

Using Bayesian Networks to Simulate eGFR Trajectories

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Background: With the widespread advent of electronic health records (EHR) systems and the routine collection of big datasets with extensive patient data, new insights can be gained around progression of conditions such as chronic kidney disease (CKD). However, missing data are unavoidable when analyzing EHR data. The objective of this study is to create a personalized data-driven model of longitudinal laboratory data, for patients with CKD or at risk for CKD that simulates missing values over time and predict $\geq 40\%$ decline in eGFR over a 1-year period.

Methods: Here, we expand on the utility of the CURE-CKD Registry, which is a comprehensive EHR database of ~ 3.9 million individuals curated from a repository of >10 million individuals, between 2006-2020 at University of California, Los Angeles Health (UCLA) and Providence St. Joseph Health (PSJH). The database includes multiple observations, with and without missing values, related to CKD and CKD risk factors. The CURE-CKD registry consists of a study entry date (the time of the first eGFR lab measurement), an entry period (time zero period -T0 -consisting of 90 days of follow up from study entry), and 14 years follow up period. Using the study entry, entry period, and the first year of average eGFR values, we built a simulation model for eGFR trajectories using discrete Bayesian Networks (BNs). BNs represent the joint probability distribution over all random variables. To train, validate, and test our BN model across different time points in CURE-CKD, we split the UCLA-specific portion (232k patients) of the Registry into datasets of 60%, 20%, and 20%, respectively, with the outcome variable of $\geq 40\%$ decline in eGFR over the average annual eGFR from the entry period measurement. To learn the structure of the BN, we used the RAUS (Ranking Approaches for Unknown Structures) software. We used GeNie to train, test, and visualize our model. We then externally validated this BN using the PSJH dataset (2,683,357 patients) from the CURE-CKD Registry.

Results: Results are reported for every subset used in our analysis. Model performance was consistent across the validation and test set. Moreover, external validation of the model demonstrated model generalization in the separate PSJH dataset. The validation set was also used to select the threshold (0.14) of classifying an individual's risk of $\geq 40\%$ eGFR decline as *true* or *false*. On the UCLA validation and test set our model had an AP (average precision) score of 0.033 and 0.033, respectively and an AUC of the ROC (Receiver's Operating Characteristic) of 0.737 and 0.764, respectively. The external test set (PSJH) had an AP and AUC ROC of 0.16 and 0.708, respectively. Model PVV and sensitivity on the UCLA test set and the PSJH external test set were 0.020 and 0.012 and 0.715 and 0.678, respectively.

Conclusion: In this study we have built a machine learning model that can be used to simulate eGFR trajectories and outcomes. Moreover, we accurately simulated clinical data values when missing and predicted the risk of $\geq 40\%$ decline in eGFR per year. We find that our proposed model generalizes well across datasets from the two health systems. Future work involves the development of dynamic Bayesian networks (DBNs) to model the entire follow up period of the CURE-CKD registry for both health systems.